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An Analysis of Meditative Realism through the Novels of Vikas Sharma

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Abstract:

This research article proposes to discuss the novels of Vikas Sharma in the light of Meditative Realism. Different theories of existential reality, based on the Indian Schools of Philosophy, have been introduced. As these philosophical principles are descriptive, they facilitate an individual with independent self-analysis. It depends on the mental environment of the truth-seekers whether they follow or reject them. Indian intellectuals can hardly escape from the careful considerations of these principles. The narratives in the novels of Vikas Sharma appear to bring forth the realism blended with the romantic approaches of life. His realism sparks with the enlightening principles of Indian philosophers. He focuses his narratives on the philosophical considerations of Vedanta including Charavaka, Buddha and Mahavira. The article deals with the analytical study of the narratives and highlights the deeds and mindset of the leading characters in given situations in his famous novels.

Keywords: Epistemology, Philosophy, Culture, Materialistic, Consumerism, Virtual, Sensuous, Prudence.

Introduction

The term “Meditative Realism” is proposed to discuss the existence of human beings in the light of Indian Schools of Philosophy. India has witnessed the radical changes in every walk of life for the past two decades. A few changes which have challenged us are financial meltdown, occurrence of pandemic disease, and terrorism. Currently, the rise of an ardent desire for change has been felt globally. We need the change that may grant a sense of

security, certainty and continuity to our existence. This change may be seen through physical, mental and spiritual spheres. Meditative Realism refers to the practical approach of an intellectual to realise the reality of human existence after following any one principle or more than one principle propounded by Indian Schools of Philosophy. It is something beyond the western ontological or philosophical terms that have been coined since the inception of the current century.

Indian Pre-epistemology (Purva Mimamsa) states that the essence of Vedas is righteousness (Dharma) and recommends its practice to earn merits for securing heaven after departure from this world. On the other side, Indian Post-epistemology (Uttara Mimamsa), also known as Vedanta, recommends following the teachings of the spiritual or mystic contemplations inherent in the Upanishads rather than the instructions related to rituals and various types of sacrifices. Indian epistemology stands as a divine lighthouse to explore the philosophy of human existence and emphasises realising the ultimate reality at one's convenience. There are mainly two schools of Indian intellectuals who explored truth and propounded their philosophical principles. The ancient one, with its faith in the authenticity of Vedas, is the Orthodox School of Indian Philosophy consisting of six sub-divisions, namely:

Advaita

Visishtadvaita

Dvaita

Dvaitadvaita

Suddhadvaita

Achintya Bheda-Abheda

The next one, without its faith in the authenticity of Vedas is the Unorthodox School of Indian Philosophy consisting of mainly three sub-divisions, namely:

Charavaka Philosophy

Buddhist Philosophy

Jain Philosophy.

Adi Shankaracharya is the chief exponent of the Advait (Non-dualism) philosophy. He explores that the individual self (Atma) is the Ultimate Self (Brahman) and at the moment of realising this truth, the individual self gets liberated. Ramanujacharya is the spiritual advocate of the Visishtadvaita (Qualified Non-dualism) philosophy. He states that the individual self is the part of the Ultimate Self, so the latter is as Unique as an organ is a part

of the body but it is not the body itself. Madhavacharya is the exponent of Dvaita (Dualism) philosophy. He considers the individual self and the Ultimate Self as two different entities, and Bhakti as the route to eternal salvation. Nimbakacharya is the founder of Dvaitadvaita (Dualistic Non-dualism) philosophy. He explores the Ultimate Self as the highest reality. Vallabhacharya is the exponent of Shuddhadvaita (Pure Non-dualism) philosophy. He states that the individual self and the Ultimate Self are the same purely. Chaitanya Mahaprabhu is the exponent of Achintya-Bheda-Abheda (Inconceivable-Different-Indifferent) philosophy. He considers that the individual self is both different and indifferent from the Ultimate Self.

Charvaka Philosophy recommends that one must derive as much pleasure as one can since death is the ultimate truth and the end of humans, and the concept of any other world is mere illusion. Buddhist Philosophy, as propounded by Siddhartha Gautama, maintains an arm's distance from the issue of existence or non-existence of God and the traditional scriptures. According to Buddha, the world is full of sorrows and sufferings, so one must seek liberation. Jain Philosophy, as conceived by Swami Mahavira, emphasises the principle of anekantavada, which holds the consideration that the "reality is perceived differently from different points of view, and that no single point of view is completely true." (Schools)

Vikas Sharma is well-versed in Indian Philosophy, literature, politics, economics and history etc. and leading an age, that needs meditative modes of writing for bridging the gap between the virtual world and the real world. There is no shed of doubt in claiming that he is the most outstanding signature of the meditative realism that should be acknowledged as a step ahead to the plain realism in literary manifestation of the current writers. The leading characters of his novels should be analysed in the light of cultural shift. In dealing with the changing cultural value, his narratives spark with the reflection of meditative realism. Living in a consumerist society, our current generation is getting caught in the clutches of an unending competition to create a fake sense of dignity. It has become a dominant habit to invest money to impress others. Owing to blind imitation, the current youths are becoming hallowed inside. Since they are in a hurry and don't deem it necessary to differentiate between the need and necessity, the demands are getting decided not by the consumers but by the market itself. All these issues are nicely highlighted in the novels of Vikas Sharma.

Discussion

“Love’s Not Time’s Fool”, the debut novel in English by Vikas Sharma, scintillates the meditative realism. The novel brings out the love story of Richa who suffers from the unfulfilled marital bliss at her prime age of womanhood. Having spent her student life in the U.S.A. with her parents, she gets caught in the clutches of the western culture leading to false love affair with Robert Lee. In order to lead a legal and fresh married life, she comes back to India where a well established business man, Malya, becomes her husband. Since he is often out on his business tour partly due to work but mostly due to his sudden impotency, she keeps herself busy in studying the books on literature, culture, history and current affairs. Richa is thrown in a situation that leads her to search an alternative so that her physical and emotional needs may be met. She gets her needs addressed by winning Abhi, a youth who has come from his village to prepare for I.A.S.

Despite her unpleasant beginning of marital bliss, she succeeds in achieving a secured and self-made life partner at the end. She does not undermine the existing social norms and resolves to maintain “self dignity at every cost”. Her intuition that “social consideration could not be given up forever” (Love’s Not 143) is a meditative reality. “After all, a person is a social animal. He /she may have animal instincts and yet chastity, fortitude, righteousness, kindness, forgiveness, etc. have been accepted as part and parcel of character in human society” (143). At the same time, she regards many of the traditional conditionings for the women as pretty extraneous elements and keeps them at an arm’s length in her personal affairs. In every challenging situation, she struggles to seek appropriate solution and does not lose hope to turn every odd into even. Keeping an eye on the socio-economic and socio-ethical changes, she meditates on her ongoing as well as new projects to make them run dynamically. Needs of the body and playfulness of the mind are well distinguished through the scenes and romantic incidents. Placed on the threshold of her full bloom youth, Richa not only remains quenching her sexual thirst frankly but also engages herself in maintaining her financial position, performing philanthropic deeds and “offering prayers to Lord Krishna to seek mental peace” (Love’s Not 171) consciously.

The novelist has meditated on the different forms of the emerging Indian women and kneaded them in the novel to mirror the stark realities attentively. Juxtaposing the themes ranging from love and lust to sainthood and liberation, the novel sparks the varieties of

learning pertaining to literature, economics, politics, history, management, religion and spirituality.

“498A: Fears and Dreams” is the next novel which explores Vikas Sharma’s meditative realism at different levels of its structure and narrative. Themed on the cases of dowry and marriage break, the novel deals with the principles of grand elements leading to a successful married life. It is certainly the result of deep meditation that makes the novelist bring forth the different causes of break up between the young couples. Despite being raised in a simple family, Tanvi expects a sophisticated life style and luxurious means from her husband, Jatin who is a diploma holder looking after the construction of L&T Co. Owing to her imprudent decision, she gets separated and received a good sum of money from Jatin’s family in exchange of her F.I.R. under 498-A. Later on, she remarried to a widower, Advocate Sharma, aged more than double to her. As Sharma is unfit to cater her emotional and bodily needs, she diverts her attention towards his son, Pratiyush and enjoys love-making consciously. This physical relationship between them is beyond plain realism that teases marriage and pleases life ironically. Meditating upon the marriage, the novelist writes, “Marriage is regarded as bliss in itself and people get married all over the world to have loving wives, the queen of their dreams and women hope to meet the prince of their hopes” (Fears 67). On the other side, reversal of fortune takes place in the life of Jatin as he is settled in New Jersey, U.S.A. with the new name Joe given by Joseph, who has accepted the former as a son. Since Joseph has lost his wife and son, Jatin becomes the heir to the entire assets belonging to the former. Jatin, with his new name Joe, got the pleasing company of Sophia, whose husband had died in Afghanistan during his posting. Sophia and Jatin are united in the marriage tie and start living a prosperous life. In a state of settled married life, the couple launched and managed the joint projects that added beauty to their pleasure and satisfaction.

Tanvi meditates on her imprudent decision, but it is meaningless to cry over spilled milk. She is responsible for her own misery, on account of uncontrolled greed, unquenched lust and hasty conclusions in decision-making. Despite the shortcuts taken by Tanvi, the style and narrative structure of the novel sustain our interest, expecting something better ahead of her present plight. Jatin, Sophia and Tanvi are the products of the novelist’s meditative realism blended with romantic sensibility.

“Ashes and Fire” narrates the bold and heroic life story of Suvidha against complex and adverse situations. Despite her unending struggles, Suvidha remains undefeated. She

possesses a formidable determination to face every challenge boldly. She is not fated to enjoy an appropriate conjugal bliss on account of the mental agony of her husband caused by the anti-social elements. Her husband finds incapable to bear the mental torture and passes away from this world leaving Suvidha with three children behind him. Owing to quite an early death of her husband, she has got to shoulder the responsibility of bringing up three children. With the due support of her loving father, Suvidha sets up the Senior Secondary School and Technical Management Institute. As her institutes have begun to run nicely, she looks for a partner who may address her physical and emotional needs. In her attempt to quench her dire physical needs, she shifts her attention from one person to another continuously, but each attempt proves vain to provide permanent security and pleasure. Apart from her private issues, she has to fight with anti-social elements that are in operation in different forms. Having iron willpower, she faces the gangsters boldly and does not hesitate to shoot them whenever they cause disaster to her family and herself. Despite her alarming mental agony related to sensual pleasure, she shows adamant willpower and self-trust. As she has been a student of literature, she knows what to do and how to live in the world of growing materialism and consumerism.

“Ideas and Events” focuses on the innovative invention of medical science through the academic interest of Sandhya. She creates a bio-chemical giant named Youngstein, invested with superhuman power to perform deeds at her wish. Owing to her medical profession, she has no time to spare for her personal life, but creation of the giant vindicates her innate desire to have an extraordinary man obey her. Finally, she faces a mental dilemma due to misuse of her knowledge. The narrative highlights the dreams of the young scientist shaping into reality. Sandhya’s sister, Vindhya, is juxtaposed to show the academic interest of the youth generation. Her academic career could bear no fruits as expected. As life is not a straight line, Vindhya has to face a complex situation due to a lecherous and lusty youth, Apurva Karan. The Romantic visions of both the sisters merge with the ground reality of the earth.

“I.A.S. Today” deals with the challenges faced by an I.A.S. aspirant and I.A.S. officer. Romesh, a true follower of Mahatma Gandhi and hailing from a rural upbringing, concentrates on I.A.S. examination and gets selected. During training, he falls in love with his trainee colleague, Trishala, who comes from an urban background. With the consent of their parents, they are united and live happily. On the other hand, some friends of Romesh do not care for their studies and take part in anti-social activities. As the gang of these spoilt

youths operates in the same city where Romesh is posted, quite a challenging situation arises for Romesh to deal with. The romantic pleasure of newly coupled Romesh and Trisahala often gets lost in dealing with the administrative work. They concentrate on practicing justice, but it becomes difficult for them to give real shape. “Quite often they felt forced to compromise with the local politicians but never extinguished the lamp of justice” (I.A.S 140).

The novel, ‘Sana’, deals with the fantastic story of Sana, who is not satisfied with her husband due to his irregular attention to cater her physical needs and glamorous dreams. Since she has failed to choose the partner of her dream and got united in the marriage bond at the will of her father, she looks for a suitable youth to respond to her. Beginning with her husband’s friend, she carries on enjoying extramarital affairs with as many youths as she finds fit to satisfy her sensuous hunger. With the financial aid and assistance of her prosperous father, she has established two Senior Secondary Schools. She takes pride in managing the schools and tries her best to facilitate the institutes with every modern equipment and accessory. She secures an imminent position in the society. She finds a free space to celebrate her present, leaving the past behind. The novel exposes the practices of adultery at various levels, extending from family to the corporate world. The virtual reality has been contrasted with the meditative reality through the cultured life of Sana’s husband. It depends on the readers as to how they get rid of the virtual glamour of the material pursuit.

Media Revolution 20230 is the tenth novel in English authored by Vikas Sharma, getting published in 2024. The novel covers up the familial, social, economic and political structures of three generations, starting in 1960 and continuing until 2030. The Romantic sensibility of the novelist intertwines well with the fabric of meditative realism as he witnesses and then narrates the events through a simple, effective and transparent structure. Characters are portrayed to face the changes taking place in the socio-economic scenario. The novel falls under the category of a campus fiction. The power play of money and politics is delineated as the undercurrent of University working system. The themes of love, marriage, family, right, duty, righteousness, spirituality have been projected with meditative deliberations.

The novel opens with the detailed descriptions of socio-political changes in Independent India. Kantyogi enrolls at Lucknow University to pursue a Bachelor of Arts with Honors. He presents his research article with self confidence, good communication skills and

analytical ability. Ujjawala feels attracted towards Kanyogi because of his extraordinary talent. Since Ujjawala hails from a well established family, she tries to persuade Kanyogi to have fun with her, however he shows his firm determination not to waste time and carries on working hard to achieve remarkable position in M.A. (English). As expected, he gets a lectureship in the English Department of Lucknow University. Ujjawala also secures the lectureship in the same department of the university due to her mother's friendship with the wife of the Head of the English Department. With the consent of the parents, Ujjawala and Kanyogi are united in a sacred marriage knot and started living in Lucknow. They take up a side business of the sole distributor of Tata Steel products in U.P. on the suggestion and support of Ujjawala's father who is the Depty Manager of Tata steels in the U.S.A. Apart from teaching, Ujjawala, with the help of Kanyogi, diverts her attention to publish the newspaper, *The Sun-Rays*.

During the annual examination of the university, Ujjawala catches a student, Shyam Mohan, cheating and forwards the case for legal action. Shyam Mohan seeks the help of his fellow students who are making a plan to teach a lesson to Ujjawala. The angry students cause significant harm to her printing press, and lodge an F.I.R. against Ujjawala and Kanyogi. An inquiry committee has been formed to investigate the facts whether they run business as complaint has been made by the students. As Ujjawala has often published the illegal deeds of the politicians, they find the fitting opportunity to get her terminated from the job. Being politically manipulated, the Vice Chancellor shows his strict stance that he would not compromise on the issue of running a side business unless Ujjawala resigns her job. Finally, Ujjawala has to resign from her job. Despite her honest deeds, she has been devoid of the teaching job but devoted wholeheartedly to flourishing her publication unit. She succeeds in editing two magazines and establishing a College for Arts and Mass Communication. She keeps mediating on the several issues of national interest and writing articles regularly. Her articles on "Determinism" and "Expectations In 2030", which is published in National Patrika, bear the fruit of her persistent effort. Her article on "Determinism" throws light on her existential reality:

It is generally seen that people blame their fate/destiny or God for their misfortunes, poverty, illiteracy, ignorance and failures in life. They don't know that success can be achieved with the righteousness and firm faith in a bright future. (Media 149)

Conclusion

Juxtaposing the rural and urban life conditions from different angles, Vikas Sharma, on account of his romantic sensibility, has experimented with a unique structure of suspending the disbelief of a fictitious narrative. His narrative structure sustains the readers' interest by enabling them to stay tuned for something new and dive into their past, present and future through the various events, images and characters. We are magically bound to read more between the lines than in the lines. The roles of Media, academic institutions, villages, youth power and political willpower have been considered for national building. His novels, at times, appear to swing between the modernist and postmodernist mindsets but suddenly cross the limits and reach beyond both. His writing bears the stamp of a meta-modernist approach. Changing family structure and cultural shift are two significant factors, which compel us to speculate on self identity and existence in the crowd of material seekers. Despite the ups and downs in life, an honest approach to the sense of duty towards the family, society, profession and nation has been discussed through the thinking and doing of the leading characters. His meditative realism juxtaposes the narratives of cultural loss and cultural promotion together so beautifully that the readers feel themselves as part and parcel of the plots in some way.

Works Cited:

Sharma, Vikas. *Ashes & Fire*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2023.

---. *.498 A : Fears and Dreams*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2022.

---. *I. A. S. Today*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2021.

---. *Ideas and Events*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2023.

---. *Love's Not Time's Fool*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2021.

---. *Media Revolution*. Diamond Pocket Books, New Delhi, 2024.

Schools of Indian Philosophy.

<https://www.drishtiiias.com/to-the-ooints/paper4/schools-of--indian-philosophy#:~:text=These%20are%20known%20as%20Vaishesika,scholarly%20discourse%20in%20the%20country>. Accessed 31 August 2024.